

Electrochemical Response of α/β -peptides: Influence of the Peptide Length, Stereochemistry and Self-Assembly on the Performance of Peptide-Based Electrochemical Sensors

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The electrochemical response of α/β -peptides with (L-Ala- β -Fpg)_n sequence, where β -Fpg refers to *syn* 3-amino-2-(2-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropanoic acid, has been investigated examining the effects of the peptide length ($n = 1-3$), the stereochemistry of the $\beta^{2,3}$ -diaryl-amino acid and their self-assembly. α/β -Peptides have been deposited by drop-casting on a conducting polymer (CP) film, which is previously electropolymerized on a stainless steel conducting substrate. The current-potential response of the CP coated by the different studied peptides suggests that, for α/β -peptides, the role played by the electron transport through intermolecular stacking of aromatic side groups prevails over peptide length and stereochemistry. In order to prove such a hypothesis, the experimental conditions used to achieve an ordered self-assembly are optimized for one of the α/β -peptides. The achieved self-assembled structures, which consist of well-defined long microfibers, considerably improve the electrochemical response of the CP. Finally, the prepared α/β -peptide-based electrodes are used to electrochemically detect the oxidation of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH). The analytical parameters are better for electrodes with well-defined peptide microfibers than for uncoated CP, corroborating the importance of π - π stacking interactions in the response of α/β -peptides.

studies on peptide self-assembly and have gained some understanding of it.^[5-10] Due to such inherent advantages, peptide nanomaterials are well-established, versatile, and biologically inspired materials that have broad application prospects in the field of materials science. Indeed, well-ordered and nanostructured peptide-based biomaterials can be used in the fields of nanotechnology, nanomedicine, and bionanotechnology.^[11-16]

In the last decade, the interest in peptides has been extended to the field of bioelectronics,^[17,18] being mainly used to functionalize active materials in field-effect transistors,^[19,20] piezoelectric energy harvesters,^[21-23] and optoelectronic devices.^[24,25] Developments in such field have been extensively reviewed over the last few years.^[26-28] Within the context of bioelectronics, peptides have also been incorporated into electrochemical sensors, even though they are usually employed as recognition elements of physiological

compounds instead of electroactive materials.^[29-33] Indeed, peptides with a specific sequence display the same specificity to target as proteins, which makes them an ideal replacement in the recognition events for electroanalysis. Moreover, peptides

1. Introduction

Peptides can self-assemble into various nanostructures that, generally, show good biocompatibility and biological activity.^[1-4] In recent decades, many scientists have conducted comprehensive

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generally display better mechanical stability against heat, light, and shear stress, as well as better chemical and conformational stability than that of proteins.^[33]

Depending on their structure, the conducting properties of many peptides can be explained in terms of proton transport,^[34–38] electron transfer, or the coupling of both. The proton transfer conduction mechanism along peptide assemblies in hydrated conditions was found to be enhanced not only by acidic and basic residues but also by aromatic residues.^[34,35] Besides, peptides bearing an adequate density of residues with aromatic side chains (e.g., Tyr, Trp and Phe) are particularly suitable to promote electron transfer through an electron hopping mechanism.^[39] For example, in the case of Phe-containing peptides, this was observed for molecules that do not contain redox cofactors.^[40,41] Thus, aromatic side groups favor electron delocalization in peptides through π - π stacking interactions, supporting a situation similar to that found in aromatic semiconducting polymers when the following two conditions are fulfilled: i) the distance and orientation between the aromatic side chains of neighboring residues allows the formation of delocalized states through π - π orbital interactions;^[42] and ii) peptide molecules are self-assembled to facilitate long-range periodic delocalization along the supramolecular structure.^[21]

In addition to the primary structure (i.e., peptide sequence) and the formation of appropriate self-assemblies,^[41,43] other factors related to the molecular structure, such as the peptide length and the peptide stereochemistry, can play a crucial role in electron delocalization along aromatic peptides. Studies on redox-active ferrocene (Fc)-labelled helical peptides showed that the electron transfer rate increased with the molecular length.^[44] The effect of stereochemistry, which obviously affects the assembly of aromatic peptides^[45–47] but is also expected to influence the intramolecular contribution to the electrical response of the peptides, has never been investigated to the best of our knowledge.

On the other hand, the use of β -peptide foldamers as materials capable to adopt regular, compact and tunable conformations is a long history that started in 1984, when a poly(β -peptide) was found to adopt a well-defined helical structure with features similar to those of α -helix in poly(α -peptides).^[48] The α -like helix of the poly(β -peptide) in question, poly(α -isobutyl- β ,L-aspartate), which bared an isobutoxycarbonyl group stereoregularly attached to the α -carbon of the repeating unit, was found to convert into a 4_1 -helix upon heating or immersion in light alcohols for a few minutes.^[49] In addition to helical conformations, extended conformations were identified by X-ray diffraction and polarized infrared spectroscopy when the isobutyl group was replaced by methyl and ethyl groups.^[50] After that, Seebach^[51] and Gellman^[52] independently reported the helical structures of β -peptides and coined the term “foldamer”.^[53] Since then, β -peptide foldamers have been extensively studied and reviewed.^[54–56]

A plethora of secondary structures has been found for peptides that combine α - and β -amino acids (α/β -peptides).^[57–59] In recent years, Gelmi and coworkers^[60,61] have been interested in the synthesis and self-assembly of α/β -peptides containing *syn*-3-amino-2-(2-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropanoic acid (β -Fpg) since the aromatic aryl groups, the lipophilic fluorine atom, and the extended conformation typically driven by *syn*- $\beta^{2,3}$ -amino acids,^[62] were ex-

Figure 1. Chemical structure of the (L-Ala- β -Fpg)_n α/β -peptides studied in this work: a) dipeptides ($n = 1$); b) tetrapeptides ($n = 2$); and c) hexapeptide ($n = 3$).

pected to induce the formation of well-shaped micro- and nanostructures. More specifically, dipeptides involving L-Ala and such $\beta^{2,3}$ -diaryl-amino acid with the appropriate stereochemistry (i.e., β -2S,3S-Fpg) were found to form well-defined nanofibers stabilized by intermolecular hydrogen bonds, π - π stacking, as well as C_{π} -H \cdots O and C_{π} -H \cdots F interactions.^[61] Also, when combined with the L-Arg-L-Ala sequence in a short tripeptide, β -2S,3S-Fpg organized forming spherical assemblies with an average diameter of 675 ± 30 nm, as determined by DLS.^[63] Furthermore, the α/β -hexapeptide containing three units of L-Ala- β -2R,3R-Fpg was found to form well-defined fibrils with electronic conductive properties (i.e., up to 32 mV when a potential of 1.5 V was applied).^[64]

In this work, we exhaustively investigate the current-potential response of (L-Ala- β -Fpg)_n α/β -peptides (**Figure 1**), examining the influence of the peptide length (i.e., $n = 1, 2$, and 3), the stereochemistry of the $\beta^{2,3}$ -diaryl-amino acid (i.e., (L-Ala- β -2R,3R-Fpg)_n and (L-Ala- β -2S,3S-Fpg)_n) and the self-assembly. More specifically, the dipeptides (**DRR** and **DSS**; **Figure 1a**), tetrapeptides (**TRR** and **TSS**; **Figure 1b**), and hexapeptide (**HRR**; **Figure 1c**) have been studied. Peptides have been used as part of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT)-based electrochemical sensors, and their performance has been evaluated by analyzing the detection of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH). The variation of this coenzyme, which is present in all living cells, in the extracellular medium serves to identify bacterial growth, thus anticipating bacterial infections, as shown by in vitro and ex vivo assays.^[65–67] By comparing the response of the different sensors toward NADH, the role of the studied peptides as components of electrochemical biosensors has been assessed.

Figure 2. a) Sketch showing the preparation of PEDOT/peptide layers onto the steel conducting substrate. b) FTIR spectra of PEDOT and PEDOT/peptide layers. c) UV-vis absorption spectra and d) E_g values of the α/β -peptides dissolved in dichloromethane (5 mg mL⁻¹).

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. PEDOT/Peptide Coatings

It has been reported that charge transfer between peptide assemblies and conducting substrates is significantly enhanced when a signal amplification element is incorporated into such interface, as for example, graphene oxide, metallic and inorganic nanostructures (e.g., nanoparticles), and conducting polymers (CPs).^[69–74] Among CPs, poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) has been shown to not only amplify the electrochemical response and stability at the interface enhancing electron transfer,^[75–80] but is also capable of increasing the technological potential of peptides in the field of electrochemical detection enhancing the chemical (compositional) selectivity.^[78–80]

For this purpose, a PEDOT layer was electropolymerized on the Kapton-uncoated steel, as is described in the Methods section, and α/β -peptides were drop-casted on the surface of the layer (**Figure 2a**). FTIR spectra of the PEDOT layer alone and with the five studied α/β -peptides deposited on the surface of the CP are compared in **Figure 2b**. PEDOT layer showed characteristic bands at 1591 and 1485 cm⁻¹ (asymmetrical and symmetrical C=C stretching in the thiophene ring, respectively), and 1258 and 1087 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C vibrations).^[81] The FTIR spectrum of all PEDOT/peptide samples is dominated by the peptide fingerprints displaying an intense, sharp peak centered at 1736 cm⁻¹ (ester bond), and peaks at 1567 cm⁻¹ (amide II) and 1215 cm⁻¹ (amide III).^[82]

The UV-vis absorption spectra of the free peptides are displayed in **Figure 2c**. It is observed that the spectra of peptides exhibit two absorption peaks at ≈ 238 and 263 nm, which have been

attributed to the π - π^* transitions of the aromatic ring without and with the fluorine atom, respectively. In order to estimate the electron transfer intrinsic to α/β -peptide molecules, the electronic band-gap energy (E_g), which was defined as the onset energy for the π - π^* transition at the lowest wavelength, was estimated using the relation of Tauc.^[83] Results, which are displayed in Figure 2d, indicate that the E_g ranges from 4.08 eV (TRR) to 4.25 eV (HRR). These values are significantly higher than those observed for semiconductors, which are typically comprised between 1.5 and 2.2 eV. On the other hand, the E_g of PEDOT, as determined from the corresponding UV-Vis spectrum (Figure S1, Supporting Information), is 1.57 eV. On the other hand, the absorption spectra of the PEDOT/peptide systems were dominated by CP, and no notable change was detected regardless of the α/β peptide deposited (Figure S2, Supporting Information), suggesting that the coating will not negatively affect the electrochemical response of PEDOT.

The cyclic voltammograms and the Nyquist plots recorded for PEDOT/DRR and PEDOT/DSS are compared with those of the control (i.e., PEDOT alone) in Figure 3a,b. It is worth noting that the deposited peptide coatings were not damaged by the phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution used as the electrolytic medium for the electrochemical assays, which was attributed to the insolubility of all the studied peptides in aqueous media. The electrochemical response of the two peptide-containing systems is smaller than that of the control, as is reflected by the fact that the areas of the voltammograms recorded for PEDOT/DRR and PEDOT/DSS are smaller than that of PEDOT (Figure 3a). Consistently, the diameters of the semicircles are larger for PEDOT/DRR and PEDOT/DSS than for PEDOT in the Nyquist plots (Figure 3b), which indicates that electrical resistance is higher for the former than for the latter. This insulating effect is much more pronounced for PEDOT/DRR than for PEDOT/DSS, which is consistent with the organization of the peptide molecules on the PEDOT layer. Indeed, SEM micrographs show the heterogeneous and porous morphology of the PEDOT layer (Figure 3c), which is attributed to the linear growth of PEDOT chains that are exclusively formed by α - α linkages (i.e., the β -positions of the thiophene ring are occupied by the dioxane ring),^[84] becomes hindered when DRR and DSS peptides are deposited onto it. Interestingly, DRR displays a homogeneous but unstructured organization (Figure 3d), while DSS shows the formation of small spherical agglomerates at the surface (Figure 3e), which are indicative of some, but still poor, ordering in a self-assembly process. As a consequence of such organization, the electrochemical response and electrical resistance are slightly higher and lower, respectively, for PEDOT/DSS than for PEDOT/DRR ($R_p = 100$ and $348 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively).

The cyclic voltammograms and Nyquist plots of PEDOT/TRR and PEDOT/TSS are compared with those of the control in Figure 4a,b. As occurred for the dipeptides, the electrochemical response and electrical conductivity of PEDOT decrease when the tetrapeptides are deposited onto it. However, the two coated PEDOT films exhibit differences between them, especially in terms of electrical resistance. Specifically, the electrochemical activity of PEDOT/TRR is slightly larger than that of PEDOT/TSS, while the resistivity of the former is around half of the latter (i.e., $R_p = 255$ vs $453 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$). It is worth noting that such R_p are fully consistent with the surface morphology of the peptide lay-

ers that, despite being unstructured for both TRR and TSS, it is more porous for the former than for the latter (Figure 4c,d). Obviously, these R_p values are closer to those obtained for PEDOT/DRR (Figure 3d), which also showed a disordered organization forming an amorphous-like layer, than to those of the partially ordered PEDOT/DSS (Figure 3e).

Figure 5 displays the results obtained for PEDOT/HRR. As occurred for the dipeptides and tetrapeptides, HRR tends to self-assemble, forming a disordered coating that reduces the electrochemical activity and electrical conductivity of PEDOT. However, both the current-response and the electrical resistivity ($R_p = 51 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$) of PEDOT/HRR (Figure 5a,b) are comparable to those of PEDOT/DSS (Figure 4a,b), which have been attributed to the surface porosity. Thus, PEDOT/HRR exhibits a network of interconnected micrometric and submicrometric pores that favor both the flux of ions and charge transport (Figure 5c). It should be noted that while these results suggest that the electrochemical response is worse with increasing peptide length, generalizations of this idea should be taken with caution. This is because (L-Ala- β -Fpg)_n peptides with $n > 3$ could undergo a conformational change that would result in a different self-assembly and, consequently, a different electrochemical response.

In general, the complete absence of order (except for DSS, which showed partial order) observed for the α/β -peptide coatings deposited on PEDOT has been attributed to the extra carbon atom of the β -amino acid (β -Fpg). In such peptides, the kinetically driven formation of intra- and intermolecular π - π interactions (i.e., using volatile solvents like dichloromethane) seems to be precluded, independently of the peptide length and stereochemistry. Clearly, the results in this work are different from those obtained with aromatic α -peptides following the same methodology.^[79] In Phe-based α -peptides, the key factors were the stereochemistry and the length of the peptide since self-assembled structures with fibrillary morphology were rapidly formed when depositing the α -peptide solutions in dichloromethane on the PEDOT films. On the contrary, the incorporation of β -Fpg, which affects the topology of the π - π stacking interactions by increasing the length of the backbone, hinders the formation of self-assembled structures and negatively affects the electrochemical response of the CP layer. In fact, as it will be shown in the next sections, the electrochemical response of the studied α/β -peptides only improves when the experimental conditions used for the deposition on PEDOT are optimized. More specifically, when polar solvents with low volatility are used in that process, the thermodynamically driven formation of ordered self-assembled structures is facilitated and, consequently, the current-potential responses increase significantly.

2.2. NADH Detection Using PEDOT/Peptide Coatings

In this section, the ability of PEDOT/peptide coatings to detect the oxidation of NADH, which is the analyte selected to detect bacterial infections,^[65,85] have been compared to that of uncoated PEDOT. Molina et al. reported a sensor that distinguished the formation of bacterial biofilms from the growth of normal eukaryotic cells by detecting the oxidation of NADH to NAD⁺ through CV.^[65,85] Eukaryotic cells present two major NADH pools, the

Figure 3. a) Cyclic voltammograms and b) Nyquist plots of PEDOT, PEDOT/DRR, and PEDOT/DSS. c–e) SEM micrographs of (c) PEDOT, (d) PEDOT/DRR, and (e) PEDOT/DSS.

cytosolic and the mitochondrial pools,^[86] while aerobic respiration reactions in such cells take place in mitochondria. However, the mitochondrial double membrane is impermeable to NADH or NAD⁺ and, therefore, mitochondrial NADH levels are maintained even upon massive depletion of cytosolic NADH.^[87,88] Instead, prokaryote cells, such as bacteria, do not have mitochondria, and their respiration occurs in the cytosol or on the inner surfaces of the cell membrane. Therefore, as prokaryotic cellular membranes are permeable to NADH and NAD⁺, a gradient was expected, and the extracellular detection of such species

was taken as an appropriate biomarker for monitoring growing bacterial infections. Accordingly, different biomedical devices (e.g., surgical meshes and sutures, and sponges for endoluminal vacuum therapy)^[67,89–91] have been functionalized with electrochemical sensors to detect bacterial growth through NADH oxidation.

The electrochemical detection of NADH was performed using a three-electrode cell in which the PEDOT or PEDOT/peptide films were used as working electrodes, as is sketched in **Figure 6a**. **Figure 6b–e** (*R*, *R*-serie) and **Figure S3** (Supporting Information)

Figure 4. a) Cyclic voltammograms and b) Nyquist plots of PEDOT, PEDOT/TRR, and PEDOT/TSS. c, d) SEM micrographs of (c) PEDOT/TRR and (d) PEDOT/TSS.

(S, S-serie) compare representative voltammograms recorded for the different working electrodes when the concentration of NADH in a 0.1 M PBS solution was gradually increased from 0 to 6 mM, while Table 1 compares the analytical parameters derived from measurements on three independent samples ($n = 3$). These indicators consist on the highest analytical sensitivity (AS), which corresponds to the slope of the calibration curve, and the

Table 1. Analytical parameters (ASs, LOD and LOQ) for detecting NADH by CV using uncoated and α/β -peptide-coated PEDOT as electrodes. Average values ($n = 3$) \pm standard deviations are displayed.

	AS [$\mu\text{A}/[\text{cm}^2 \text{mM}]$]	LOD [mM]	LOQ [mM]
Uncoated PEDOT	78.17 ± 9.13	0.13 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.07
PEDOT/DRR	49.79 ± 6.23	0.20 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.08
PEDOT/DSS	21.25 ± 3.05	0.31 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.15
PEDOT/TRR	29.88 ± 4.76	0.41 ± 0.03	1.37 ± 0.10
PEDOT/TSS	25.61 ± 3.76	0.70 ± 0.08	2.33 ± 0.25
PEDOT/HRR	30.80 ± 2.91	0.60 ± 0.11	1.99 ± 0.39
PEDOT/DSS (fibers)	1475 ± 48	0.13 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.08

lowest limits of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ, respectively), which were calculated as the ratio between k times the standard deviation of the blank (i.e., without NADH) and the slope of the calibration curve with $k = 3$ and 10 for LOD and LOQ, respectively.

As it was expected, PEDOT displays an oxidation peak at ≈ 0.4 – 0.5 V (Figure 6b, left), which corresponds to the oxidation of NADH to NAD⁺. Indeed, the position of the peak increases from 0.43 V, for 1–3 mM NADH concentrations to 0.48 V, for a concentration of 6 mM, which was reported to be due to the change in the pH associated with the redox reaction (Figure 6a).^[66,85] Other studies using PEDOT-based electrodes also reported the oxidation peak of NADH between 0.5 V (i.e., PEDOT colloidal microparticles)^[92] and 0.70 V (i.e., graphene-PEDOT:PSS composite).^[93] The LOD obtained for PEDOT was 0.13 mM only, while the AS was $78.17 \mu\text{A}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{mM})$ (Figure 6b, right).

In general, the analytical parameters obtained for all α/β -peptide-coated PEDOT electrodes are worse than those obtained for uncoated PEDOT, even though results are largely dependent on the chemical structure of the incorporated α/β -peptide (Table 1). For example, the AS, LOD, and LOQ of PEDOT/DRR are only slightly worse than those of uncoated PEDOT, while

Figure 5. a) Cyclic voltammograms and b) Nyquist plots of PEDOT and PEDOT/HRR. SEM micrographs of c) PEDOT/HRR.

the incorporation of **DSS** represents a significant impairment of the analytical parameters. Consistently, the voltammograms recorded for PEDOT/DRR not only show a very well-defined NADH oxidation peak, especially in the concentration range from 3 to 6 mM, but also a significant increase in the current density with the NADH concentration (Figure 6c). Instead, the oxidation peak and the increase of the current density with the NADH concentration were much less evident for PEDOT/DSS, as is shown in the recorded voltammograms and the corresponding calibration curve (Figure S3a, Supporting Information). Furthermore, for α/β -peptide-coated PEDOT electrodes the oxidation is detected at a slightly higher potential than for the uncoated PEDOT electrode, which has been attributed to the sensitivity of the peptides to the released H_3O^+ .

Comparison of the analytical indicators obtained PEDOT/DRR, PEDOT/TRR, and PEDOT/HRR (Table 1) reflects that the increase in the length of the α/β -peptide is detrimental to the performance of the sensor. Thus, the LOD and LOQ of the three peptides of the same series increase as follows: **DRR** < **TRR** < **HRR** and, similarly, **DSS** < **TSS**. Consistently, the oxidation peak of NADH is much less pronounced for PEDOT/TRR (Figure 6d) and, especially, for PEDOT/HRR (Figure 6e) than for PEDOT/DRR. As shown in Table 1, the analytical parameters are also better for the **TRR**-coated sensor with respect to the **TSS** one (Figure S4b, Supporting Information). Taken together, these results indicate that not only does the length of the peptide affect the electrochemical response, but also the chirality of the amino acid plays a key role in the recognition of NADH molecules. These results are in agreement with the selectivity of NADH and NAD^+ that is known to recognize and bind natural proteins,^[94] as well as specific α -peptides in biosensors.^[79]

2.3. Influence of the α/β -Peptide Self-Assembly on the Electrochemical Response and NADH Detection

SEM micrographs displayed in Figures 3–5 showed that the α/β -peptides deposited on PEDOT layers were unstructured, which hindered the electron transfer not only between the aromatic rings of neighboring peptide molecules, but also at the PEDOT-peptide interface. This is probably due to the electrochemical response and NADH detection capacity of all PEDOT/peptide electrodes, which were worse than those of uncoated PEDOT. On the other hand, among the α/β -peptides coating PEDOT, the electrochemical response and electrical resistance are slightly higher and lower, respectively, for PEDOT/DSS than for PEDOT/DRR ($R_p = 100$ and $348 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively), as also with respect to the longest peptides. As reported above, our hypothesis is that this result depends on a more ordered self-assembly process for PEDOT/DSS, even if still poor (Figure 3e), that plays an essential role in the properties of peptide-based electrodes. Since achieving self-assembly of peptides is a very tedious task, we have focused on the single peptide **DSS** to validate our hypothesis. This choice is also supported by the existence of a preliminary study on the self-assembly of **DSS** and **DRR** in which it was demonstrated that **DSS** peptide can give nanofibers, but not **DRR**.^[61] This information, together with the fact that PEDOT/DSS electrodes have an intrinsically superior electrochemical response (Figure 3a-b) in comparison to that of other peptides, prompted us to validate our hypothesis by using **DSS** peptide.

The most remarkable conditions used to investigate the self-assembly of the **DSS** on stainless steel are listed in Figure S4a (Supporting Information). These consisted of diluted peptide concentrations (0.5 and 2.0 mg mL^{-1}) in HFIP alone or mixed

Figure 6. a) Sketch of the setup used to detect NADH. Electrochemical detection of NADH at the surface of b) PEDOT, c) PEDOT/DRR, d) PEDOT/TRR and e) PEDOT/HRR: cyclic voltammograms recorded in 0.1 M PBS solutions with NADH concentrations ranging from 0 to 6 mM are displayed at the left, while the calibration plots ($n = 3$) using the current density at the oxidation peak (j) are shown at the right.

Figure 7. a–c) SEM micrographs of the microfibrillary assemblies obtained by drop casting (a) 2 mg mL^{-1} DSS in a 98:2 H_2O :HFIP mixture on stainless steel, (b) 0.5 mg mL^{-1} DSS in a 95:5 H_2O :HFIP mixture on stainless steel, and (c) 2 mg mL^{-1} DSS in a 98:2 H_2O :HFIP mixture on PEDOT. d,e) Cyclic voltammograms of PEDOT and PEDOT/DSS when the DSS peptide was drop-casted as in (c): (d) first redox cycle and (e) after 25 consecutive redox cycles.

with EtOH and H_2O . On the other hand, Figure S4b (Supporting Information) shows representative optical microscopy images of the structures observed on the surface of glass coverslips after solvent evaporation. Although relatively well-ordered assemblies were obtained from HFIP: H_2O mixtures, the definition of the microstructures clearly improved when the amount of water in the solvent:co-solvent mixture increased. Microfibrillary structures of DSS were obtained considering the following two conditions: 1) solutions containing 2 mg/mL DSS in a 98:2 H_2O :HFIP mixture, which is in good agreement with the results reported by

Bonetti et al.,^[61] and 2) solutions prepared with 0.5 mg mL^{-1} DSS in a 95:5 H_2O :HFIP mixture. SEM micrographs of the self-assembled structures obtained using such conditions are shown in Figure 7a,b. Although in both cases the self-assembled structures were well-defined and had similar characteristics (i.e., microfibers of hundreds of μm in length, and $\approx 6\text{--}10 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness), we chose to use the first condition to prepare PEDOT/DSS electrodes since the number of imperfections in the microfibers was slightly lower, suggesting that the peptide molecules were more ordered.

Figure 8. Electrochemical detection of NADH at the surface of self-assembled PEDOT/DSS. Cyclic voltammograms recorded in 0.1 M PBS solutions with NADH concentrations ranging from 0 to 6 mM are displayed at the left, while the calibration plot ($n = 3$) using the current density at the oxidation peak (j) is shown at the right.

PEDOT/DSS coatings with the α/β -peptide self-assembled into microfibrillary structures were prepared using the procedure described above (i.e., electropolymerizing PEDOT onto steel and drop-casting a 2 mg mL⁻¹ DSS solution in 98:2 H₂O:HFP). Figure 7c reflects that microfibrillary structures were also formed on the PEDOT layer, even though the thickness of the fibers was half that of those obtained on stainless steel. After carefully separating the microfibrils from the PEDOT surface, a powder was obtained, which was analyzed by X-ray diffraction. The powder diffraction pattern (Figure S5, Supporting Information) showed a high degree of order, with the same planes described in previous work for DSS single crystals obtained on glass slides by slow evaporation of the solvent at room temperature (1:1 acetonitrile:water).^[68] Based on this result, it was assumed that the microfibrillar structures formed in the PEDOT layer present the curved conformation described previously.^[68]

The cyclic voltammograms recorded for PEDOT and PEDOT/DSS, which are compared in Figure 7d, indicate that the peptide self-assembly plays a key role in the electrochemical response. Not only is the area of the PEDOT/DSS voltammogram much higher than that recorded for the electrode in which the DSS is organized in small spherical agglomerates (Figure 3a), but also than that one of uncoated PEDOT. Although the microspheres obtained when the peptide was dissolved in dichloromethane (Figure 3e) are indicative of partial molecular ordering, the formation of microfibrillary constructs (Figure 3c) required assemblies with a much higher degree of ordering.^[95] Thus, DSS microfibrillary structures favor the electron transport through both the intermolecular stacking of the aromatic side groups (i.e., π -delocalization along the individual peptide molecules) and, especially, through the PEDOT-peptide interface, which considerably enhances the electrochemical response with respect to that displayed in Figure 3a.

On the other hand, the electrochemical stability of PEDOT/DSS is higher than that of uncoated PEDOT. This is demonstrated in Figure 7e, which shows the cyclic voltammograms recorded for PEDOT and PEDOT/DSS after 25 consecutive oxidation and reduction cycles in PBS electrolytic medium. As it is usual when the scanned potential window is as wide as the one used in this work (i.e., from -0.90 to +0.90 V), the area of the voltammogram of uncoated PEDOT decreased with the increasing number of cycles. Surprisingly, Figure 7e evidences that PEDOT/DSS does not undergo any loss of electroactivity, which

is attributed to the stability of the peptide microfibrils. Thus, the electron transport at the interface between the well-ordered DSS fibrillary constructs and the PEDOT coating promotes the stabilization of the latter. Thus, the microfibrils did not undergo any structural damage or deformation after 25 redox cycles, as is demonstrated in Figure S6 (Supporting Information).

Thus, considering these very good results, the performance of the self-assembled PEDOT/DSS as an electrode to detect NADH was investigated using the electrochemical set-up described above. Its results (Figure 8) indicate that the intensity of the NADH oxidation peak increased clearly and progressively with the NADH concentration. Although the calibration profile reflects that NADH molecules reached the surface of PEDOT/DSS by conventional diffusion and oxidation, the comparison with the calibration profiles displayed in Figure 5 and Figure S3 (Supporting Information) reveals two important differences. First, the slope obtained for the electrode with microfibrillary DSS assemblies was much more pronounced than the slopes obtained for the electrodes formed by uncoated PEDOT or PEDOT coated with disordered or partially ordered peptides. This suggests that the content of electrocatalytic active sites increases when the peptide self-assembles into microfibrillary structures. Second, the electrode coated with microfibrillary DSS shows two linear regimes instead of one. The first one, which was obtained for low NADH concentrations ($\leq 250 \mu\text{M}$), defines the analytical parameters of the sensor (see Table 1), while the second regime (from 250 μM to 6 mM) also shows higher slopes than those of the calibration curves displayed in Figure 6 and Figure S3 (Supporting Information). Detailed inspection of Table 1 reveals that the AS of self-assembled PEDOT/DSS is higher than that of uncoated PEDOT, while the LOD and LOQ are practically identical for the two electrodes.

3. Conclusion

Drop-casting of the (L-Ala- β -Fpp)_n peptide solutions in dichloromethane onto PEDOT, electropolymerized on stainless steel, led to the formation of disordered (DRR, TRR, TSS, and HRR) or partially ordered (DSS) layers. As a consequence, the electrochemical response of PEDOT/peptide electrodes was smaller than that of uncoated PEDOT. This behavior has been attributed to the fact that the electron transport through intra- or intermolecular π - π stacking interactions is less efficient in

α/β -peptides than in α -peptides due to the extra carbon atom of the β -Fpg residue. Thus, stable ordered assemblies cannot be easily reached for α/β -peptides when a volatile organic solvent is used (i.e., the assembly is kinetically driven). Although the influence of the peptide length and the stereochemistry was significant, it was not enough to overcome the lack of electron transport induced by the disordered organization of the peptide layer, which acted as an insulating coating. This was confirmed by the utilization of PEDOT and PEDOT/peptide electrodes as electrochemical sensors to detect the oxidation of NADH. The analytical detection parameters of the PEDOT/peptide electrodes were comparable to or worse than those of uncoated PEDOT. Caution is required when extrapolating the effect of peptide length for $n > 3$, since conformational changes could affect the self-assembly ability and, by extension, the electrochemical response.

In order to evaluate the influence of self-assembly on the electrochemical response of α/β -peptide-based sensors, the experimental conditions to obtain microfibrillary structures of **DSS**, known to give nanofibers, were evaluated. Results showed that this hydrophobic dipeptide forms well-ordered and defined microconstructs when it is dissolved in polar solvent mixtures (i.e., 98:2 H₂O:HFIP and 95:5 H₂O:HFIP). The thermodynamically-driven formation of microfibrillary structures on PEDOT led to a significant improvement of the electrochemical response, which was attributed to the electron transport induced through the formation of ordered π - π stacking interactions. Such a hypothesis was confirmed by a proof of concept based on the detection of NADH. Results showed that the analytical parameters of the sensor improved considerably when the deposited peptide was ordered, forming microfibers, the AS being even better than that of uncoated PEDOT. These observations evidence that self-assembly is a key parameter for the electrochemical response of α/β -peptides, which reflects the need to investigate the optimal conditions necessary for the formation of ordered structures if these compounds are to be used in bioelectronic applications.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: All reagents for peptide synthesis were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Flourochem, and commercial sources and were used without further purification. All solvents were of ACS grade or higher and were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and commercial sources. 3,4-Ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT; 97%) and acetonitrile were purchased from Aldrich and used as received. Anhydrous LiClO₄ (analytical reagent grade; Aldrich) was stored in an oven at 80 °C before use. NADH and phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution were also purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Peptides: The electrochemical and electrical response of five different α/β -peptides was evaluated. Specifically, all of them were based on the (L-Ala- β -Fpg)_{*n*} sequence and protected with *tert*-butyloxycarbonyl (Boc) and methyl ester (OMe) at the *N*- and *C*-terminus, respectively (Figure 1). They were prepared according to a known procedure^[60] from L-Ala and both diastereoisomers of *syn*-3-amino-2-(2-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropanoic acid (*R,R*- and *S,S*- β -Fpg). With respect to the original protocol,^[68] synthesis of β -Fpg was successfully scaled-up from 2.5 to 29.8 mmol of the reagents. These peptides were classified in three categories according to their length: 1) two α/β -dipeptides, which differ in the stereochemistry of the $\beta^{2,3}$ -diaryl-amino acid (**DRR** and **DSS**; Figure 1a); 2) two tetrapeptides based on two repetitions ($n = 2$) of the (L-Ala- β -Fpg)_{*n*} sequence and con-

taining *R,R*- and *S,S*- β -Fpg, respectively (**TRR** and **TSS**; Figure 1b); and 3) one hexapeptide based on the (L-Ala- β -2*R*,3*R*-Fpg)₃ sequence (**HRR**; Figure 1c).

Reactions involving air-sensitive reagents were performed under a nitrogen atmosphere, and anhydrous solvents were used when necessary. Reactions were monitored by thin-layer chromatography carried out on Merck silica gel 60 F250 (0.26 mm thickness) plates with UV light ($\lambda = 254$ nm) as the visualizing agent and Ninhydrin as the developing agent. Pure products were obtained using Merck flash Silica gel (SiO₂) high-purity grade, pore size 60 Å, 230–400 mesh particle size (40–63 μ m) after column chromatography. All peptides were kept at –20 °C until use to avoid their denaturation or degradation.

Preparation and Characterization of Conducting Polymer Coated with α/β -Peptides: Steel electrodes (2.5 × 2.0 cm²) were coated with poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT), a well-known conducting polymer (CP). For this purpose, cleaned steel samples were covered with Kapton tape, leaving a central 1 × 1 cm² window (working electrode). The selected conducting substrate was immersed in a three-electrode electrochemical cell with 25 mL of an acetonitrile solution containing 50 μ M of EDOT monomer and 0.1 M of LiClO₄, as supporting electrolyte. The electrochemical set-up was completed with the counter and the reference electrodes, which were a stainless steel sheet of 2.0 × 1.0 cm² and Ag|AgCl in 3 M KCl, respectively. Then, a constant potential of 1.2 V was applied for 60 s to stabilize the system and, subsequently, a potential sweep between –0.5 V and +1.4 V was conducted at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{–1} for 60 s. All electrochemical polymerizations were performed at room temperature. The resulting dark blue PEDOT layer formed on the surface of the conducting substrate showed a thickness of 250 ± 16 μ m. Finally, the PEDOT layer was coated with the corresponding α/β -peptide by dropping 250 μ L of a dichloromethane solution of peptide (5 mg mL^{–1} solution) to completely cover the 1 × 1 cm² CP surface, and the solvent was allowed to evaporate. Peptide-coated PEDOT samples were prepared considering all the α/β -peptides displayed in Figure 1.

FTIR spectra were recorded on an FTIR Jasco 4100 spectrophotometer through an attenuated total reflection accessory (Top-plate) with a diamond crystal (Specac model MKII Golden Gate Heated Single Reflection Diamond ATR). Samples were evaluated using spectra manager software and, for each sample, 64 scans were performed between 4000 and 600 cm^{–1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{–1}.

Absorption spectra were obtained with a Shimadzu 3600 spectrophotometer equipped with a tungsten halogen visible source, a deuterium arc UV source, a photomultiplier tube UV–vis detector, and an InGaAs photodiode and cooled PbS photocell NIR detectors. Spectra were recorded in the absorbance mode using the integrating sphere accessory (model ISR-3100), the wavelength range being 300–800 nm. Single-scan spectra were obtained at a scan speed of 60 nm min^{–1} with a bandwidth of 2 nm using the UVProbe 2.31 software.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies were performed in a Focused Ion Beam Zeiss Neon 40 microscope equipped with an SEM GEMINI column with a Schottky field emission and an EDX spectroscopy system. The working distance was fixed to 5 mm, and the working voltage was 3 kV for stabilizing the resolution of the images.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) assays were performed with an Autolab VIONIC (Metrohm) potentiostat-galvanostat, which was controlled with the Intello software. A standard three-electrode cell was used to evaluate the current-potential response of the studied samples. For each studied system, the sheet with the deposited peptides was employed as the working electrode (WE), while the counter electrode (CE) and reference electrode (RE) were a platinum wire and Ag|AgCl (KCl, 3 M) electrode, respectively. The electrochemical cell was filled with 5 mL of a PBS solution (pH 7.4), which was used as the electrolytic medium. The initial and final potentials were –0.90 V, while the reverse potential was +0.90 V. The scan rate was fixed at 50 mV s^{–1}. For observing the reproducibility of results, three different samples of each system were tested. All assays were performed at 22 °C. Three replicates with independent samples were performed of all electrochemical assays to ensure reproducibility.

Self-Assembly and Deposition of Self-Assembled Microfibrillary Structures on Conducting Polymer: Self-assembly studies were focused on the **DSS**

dipeptide. More specifically, peptide-containing solutions were prepared from 100 mg mL⁻¹ stocks using hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP) as solvent. The peptide concentration was reduced by adding ethanol (EtOH) or Milli-Q water (H₂O) as co-solvents in different HFIP:co-solvent ratios (40:60, 20:80, 10:90, 5:95, and 2:98), to the stock solution to a final concentration of 0.5 or 2.0 mg mL⁻¹. Finally, 20 μL aliquots were placed on microscope coverslips and kept at room temperature (25 °C) until dryness. Optical microscopy observations were performed using a Zeiss Axioskop 40 microscope. Micrographs were taken with a Zeiss AxiosCam MRC5 digital camera.

After selecting the optimum conditions for the self-assembly, the preparation of PEDOT/DSS electrodes was performed using the procedure described above for the preparation of conducting polymer coated with α/β -peptides.

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) was performed with a Bruker D8-Discover model with a Bragg-Brentano 2 θ configuration and a Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Measurements were performed at room temperature in a range of $5^\circ < 2\theta < 50^\circ$ in steps of 0.02° during 1250 s in total. Standard powder diffraction was carried out, and the detection was performed with a Lynxeye XE-T Detector.

Electrochemical Detection of NADH: The electrochemical detection of NADH was studied by CV using a three-electrode cell and an Autolab VIONIC potentiostat-galvanostat. In this case, PEDOT films uncoated (control) and coated with an α/β -peptide were used as working electrodes. The counter and reference electrodes were identical to those described above for electrochemical characterization. Measurements were performed by adding different concentrations of NADH (from 0 to 6 mM) to the electrolytic medium, which was a 0.1 M PBS solution. The initial and final potentials were -0.20 V , and the reversal potential was $+0.80 \text{ V}$. The scan rate was 50 mV s^{-1} . Three replicates with independent samples were performed of all detection assays to ensure reproducibility.

Statistical Analysis: All experiments were conducted in triplicate using independent samples. Values were presented as the mean \pm SD. Statistical analysis has been conducted using Microsoft Excel software.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

α/β -Peptides, bioelectronics, NADH detection, self-assembly, stacking interactions

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